

European long-term ecosystem, critical zone and socio-ecological systems research infrastructure PLUS

D 7.1 TA and RA Process

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Publishable Executive Summary

Well-designed operational and administrative processes are needed to offer Transnational Access (TA) and Remote Access (RA) in the framework of the eLTER PLUS project. TA refers to in-person, physical, hands-on work by users at one or more of the eLTER sites involved in the scheme, whereas RA refers to measurement or experimental protocols defined by users and performed by site staff on their behalf. eLTER PLUS also offers Virtual Access (VA) to its data which is, however, not subject of the present document.

User groups who are offered TA and RA receive technical/scientific support and also financial reimbursement. To take part in the scheme, the users must meet the criteria defined for eligibility and results dissemination. The operational process of providing TA and RA contains the process steps:

- (1) Call for proposals,
- (2) Submission and file management,
- (3) Eligibility check,
- (4) Plausibility check by site owners,
- (5) Scientific evaluation,
- (6) Selection of projects,
- (7) Notification, and
- (8) Reporting after TA/RA is completed.

Annexes of the document are the templates provided to users for their proposals and project reporting, the template provided to the evaluators of the TA/RA proposals and the document *eLTER PLUS TA Administration for Site Owners*.

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Structure of this deliverable

To apply for Transnational Access (TA) and/or Remote Access (RA), potential users or user groups should refer to and use the following documents which are collated in the present deliverable.

- The operational/administrative/financial modalities regarding the TA scheme are described in **the document The eLTER PLUS Transnational Access (TA) and Remote Access (RA) Scheme**
- Users wishing to request access must fill in and submit the **eLTER PLUS Access Proposal Template** (Annex 1).
- After completing their site visit they must fill in the **eLTER PLUS Reporting Template** (Annex 2) prior to obtaining financial reimbursement.

All these items will be made available for download from the project website.

Evaluators of the user proposals will use the **eLTER PLUS TA/RA Proposal Evaluation Form** (Annex 3)

- Moreover, to facilitate the administrative handling of TA provision, the document **eLTER PLUS TA Administration for Site Owners** (Annex 4) is provided.
- Sites are recommended to conclude a simple agreement with their users. An example is provided as Annex 5.

Note: eLTER PLUS also offers Virtual Access (VA) to its data. Although the three access modes by eLTER PLUS are interrelated, the process how VA is performed is entirely different from the one regarding TA and RA. It is, thus, not subject of the present document.

The eLTER PLUS Transnational Access (TA) and Remote Access (RA) Scheme

eLTER PLUS offers free-of-charge opportunities for multi-national teams of researchers or for individual researchers to perform research at selected sites for the purpose of small to medium scale ecological and socio-ecological projects. The scheme will support both single-site and preferably multiple-site (i.e. requiring co-ordinated work and data synthesis across two or more sites) research projects. Funding provided to user-groups or individual researchers for projects will be awarded on a competitive basis.

Through its access scheme, eLTER PLUS opens up the eLTER Research Infrastructure (eLTER RI) and intends to attract a wide range of users, primarily from outside of the consortium. Through bottom-up calls, new and additional users shall be linked to eLTER and novel scientific applications shall be enabled and collaboration within and beyond the eLTER community shall be enlarged. Moreover, through top-down calls with pre-defined scientific frameworks for the user projects, ongoing eLTER work relating to urgent research challenges shall be supported and widened. In either case, education will be fostered to strengthen the next generation of eLTER researchers. The eLTER PLUS access scheme contributes to the generation of new data which shall be made available widely and openly. See the section on Calls for Proposals below.

All sites included in the eLTER PLUS TA and RA Scheme are equipped with state-of-the-art instrumentation to enable comprehensive ecological measurement and experimental campaigns. Likewise, state-of-the-art socio-economic research is conducted at several of them. IT-facilities are provided for data upload, storage and processing. The sites were selected to represent all biogeographic zones of the continent and they are described at the eLTER PLUS website and in the eLTER Site Catalogue.

TA refers to in-person, physical, hands-on work by users at one or more of the LTER sites involved in the scheme, whereas RA refers to protocols regarding measurements, data collection, and possibly experiments defined by users and performed on their behalf by site staff. These three modes are summarised in the below table.

Overview of eLTER access modes

This document relates to the operational aspects of transnational and remote access. Nevertheless, Virtual access is also mentioned in this table for reference and for reasons of completeness.

	Transnational access	Remote access	Virtual access
Role of users	Users perform their own on-site measurements or experiments	Users define protocols for measurements and experiments to be performed at the site(s) by local staff	Users download data from the eLTER DIP (Data Integration Platform)
Role of site staff	Explains the facilities and supervises and supports users' activities	Perform work on the users' behalf and sends results and, if needed, specimens to the users	Ensure that data are accessible to users, e.g. by producing a data file and uploading it to a cloud server
Related travel	Users or teams of users visit site(s) in person, site staff is (partly) present	Users do not travel, site staff is present at the site	Users do not travel, nor does site staff
Funding needed*	Travel costs of users and of site staff, working time of site staff	Travel costs and working time of site staff	Working time of site staff

)* see "Financial Support" below

Support offered

Technical/scientific support for TA

Supervision and training: Users will be introduced to the site, the scientific questions it addresses, its ongoing operations and the existing instrumentation. They will receive access to past data and scientific results from the permanent monitoring programmes. Site personnel will provide training to use the site's facilities and instruments, and also any supervision needed for the users' preparatory work.

Use of instrumentation: Users may take part in all ongoing routine measurements. Likewise, jointly with site personnel, particular measurement activities may be specifically set up for the users' own research. Users may also bring and use their own instruments, subject to the prior consent of the site owner.

Performing technical/scientific work for RA

Users will receive detailed information about the site and its opportunities and interact with site staff remotely through electronic media including teleconferencing. During the RA project, site staff will perform the work agreed with the selected users. The outcomes, that is data and observations, and, if needed, specimens, will be made available or sent, respectively, to the users.

Special conditions for top-down calls (both regarding TA and RA)

eLTER top-down calls for proposals pre-define a thematic framework which the user project should address. In this way, access related user projects shall be linked to ongoing eLTER work regarding priority research challenges, and before user project starts and if needed also during the project work, an exchange with highly qualified eLTER PLUS staff is offered to users for a mutual benefit.

Combination of TA and RA

eLTER PLUS encourages the users to combine TA and RA related project work. Thereby, users could hands-on test and refine a protocol they developed at one site, and thereafter have the same protocol performed at other sites remotely. In this way, the advantages of both approaches can be combined. TA enables physically visiting a site and gaining practical experiences by performing own research related work. It also provides the benefits of face-to-face interaction with and supervision by site staff. Whereas, RA enables the continuation of the work and a geographical upscaling in an environment-friendly and economically viable manner through remote work without travel. In this way, the added value of the network can efficiently be demonstrated as opposed to single-site research.

Financial support

Free of charge access: Users selected to benefit from the eLTER PLUS Access Scheme will not be charged, and can thus enjoy free access to the site(s) and all the services provided to them during TA and/or RA. Instead, the eLTER PLUS project will reimburse the eligible costs incurred by the site's host organisations as unit costs or actual costs as agreed in the project Grant Agreement.

Cost reimbursement for users: For site visits, users will receive reimbursement of least-cost travel expenses to, from and within the site. Private or rental car travel will be supported if travel by public transportation is not possible. If possible, on-site accommodation and/or on-site meals will be offered at no cost to the users. If not, the costs of reasonable accommodation in the vicinity of the site will be reimbursed and costs for food as well (see subsistence rates). Site staff will assist users in finding suitable accommodation in the vicinity of the site.

Central and de-central cost reimbursement: Costs for users will exclusively be covered by the site host organisations, that is in a decentral way. Site host organisations may claim costs for both user expenses reimbursement and for their own effort as part of their eLTER PLUS project funding.

Personnel costs: Users' personnel costs will not be covered.

Food and out-of-pocket expenses: For TA, the site host institution may provide all-inclusive subsistence rates. The amount will depend on whether meals are provided on-site or not. Subsistence rates will usually be determined in accordance with national regulations of the country where the site is located, and/or the usual practices of the site's host organisation. Alternatively, the site host institution may cover actual costs as incurred by the users instead.

Pre-payments: The scheme foresees costs reimbursement after users have fulfilled their reporting obligations. However, in justified exceptional cases, a pre-payment (e.g. to cover a flight ticket) may be granted. This decision is up to the site host organisation.

Total funds available

eLTER PLUS will make a total of 1.2 Million € available through its TA Scheme. These funds will support costs incurred by users as described above (ca. 300.000 €), and costs incurred by site host organisations during TA visits or RA performance (ca. 900.000 €). The host organisations of all the involved sites are Beneficiaries of the eLTER PLUS project.

Duration of TA

No maximum number of days is provided which a user group may spend at a site. The duration of the projects and the size of the user groups should be adequate in relation to the work to be performed. Experience shows that typically, a stay of one week per site is sufficient, however, depending on the planned work, this may differ, partly significantly, from project to project.

If a study requires several stays, e.g. related to seasonality, one project may encompass several visits to one site. In such cases, depending on funding available, two journeys to and from the site may be covered as well.

Oversubscription of sites

If users apply for TA or RA to a site, the funds of which have already been used up, such funds may be transferred from an undersubscribed site to the oversubscribed one, pending approval of both site owning organisations. Alternatively, users may be offered to perform a comparable study at another site that has unspent TA funds. As far as possible, the alternative site offered will have similar biogeographical characteristics.

Eligibility

Prerequisites for TA and RA users

eLTER PLUS offers access opportunities to user-groups or to individual researchers. In the former case, one of the group members must act as the group leader.

This user group leader or the sole user must be affiliated to an organisation in a country other than the country where the site they wish to access is located. In the case of a group of users, the majority of the group's members must also work in a country other than the country where the site is located which they wish to jointly access. For multi-site projects, this rule applies to all the sites to be accessed.

Users working for an organisation which is an eLTER PLUS Beneficiary, are in principle eligible for receiving TA and/or RA funding, however, limitations apply. This programme will not support users wishing to access a facility his/her own organisation owns.

Users not working in a European Union Member State or H2020 Associated Country are eligible, provided they do not form the majority within the respective user group. However, well-founded exceptions are possible.

There is no formal prerequisite as to the users' education or their degrees held.

Dissemination of results and data policy

Prior to receiving access, user groups must confirm that they intend to disseminate the outcomes of their study conducted under the eLTER PLUS TA/RA Scheme. Users representing SMEs (Small and Medium Enterprises) are exempt from this rule. However, also to them, publishing their results is strongly recommended, e.g. through a company newsletter.

Whatever data is collected during the visit must be made available to the site owner organisation and to the wider scientific community within a reasonable time frame and without significant delays (recommended time frame: at most two years). Again, SME users are exempt from this rule. The data policy should presume a timely pathway towards Open Access. At the end of the project, or when publications arise during the project, data should be released using a standard Open Data license and be free of intellectual property rights (IPR). The eLTER TA/RA grant should be acknowledged in all products from the access related projects.

Successful users will be asked to provide a description of their visit, including photographs, and they may be invited to write a blog and/or social media messages during their visit, describing their experiences.

Sequence of process steps

The overall process of organising TA and RA within eLTER PLUS is divided into the following steps:

1. Call for proposals
2. Submission and file management
3. Eligibility check
4. Plausibility check by site owners
5. Scientific evaluation
6. Selection of projects
7. Notification
8. Reporting after TA/RA is completed

1) Call for proposals

Research teams are encouraged to apply for access by submitting a project proposal to eLTER PLUS. The application procedure is set up as a single-stage call for proposals.

Potential users who wish to be granted TA and/or RA to the eLTER PLUS sites find the needed information about access opportunities at the project website. This includes details on the sites that users may access, their location, biogeographical characteristics and instrumentation.

eLTER PLUS distinguishes bottom-up and top-down calls. In the case of the former, users are free to articulate their own research themes, in the case of the latter, such themes are defined as a thematic framework in line with the research challenges of the project to extend/deepen

the project work jointly with users. Both cases provide many opportunities regarding education. Experiences made in the predecessor-project has shown that the eLTER access scheme is very suitable to support graduate students who conduct such studies as part of their thesis work. The below figure illustrates this approach.

Overview of eLTER PLUS access related calls for proposals.

Note: There is no dedicated educational call, but this approach is embedded in either bottom-up or top-down calls. Users' fieldwork in most cases happens during the summer months, but may also start earlier if needed.

2) Proposal submission and file management

Applicants should download and fill in the eLTER PLUS Access Proposal Template (MS Word document) and submit it to a dedicated e-mail address which will be provided on the eLTER PLUS project website and in the application related documentation. Supporting documents may be submitted as well, if needed. The template may later on be replaced by an online form. Applicants receive support during their proposal preparation in that they may send any enquiries to the eLTER PLUS Access Helpdesk. They will usually receive an answer within three working days.

Prior to formally submitting a proposal, the applicants are recommended to contact site personnel informally regarding their planned project work to check with them whether the work is feasible under the given natural and structural conditions and whether site personnel has to capacity to support this specific project work. Contact information is provided via the eLTER PLUS project website.

Calls are published annually with the following approximate timing (referring to the end of the related month):

- September: Publication of the call
- November: Deadline for submission
- February: Evaluation outcome and notification of users
- Projects typically are conducted during the summer season, but users may choose any timing as early as April.

All of the eLTER PLUS sites may be opened during a call or only a subset of them. This mostly relates to funding available.

For all proposals submitted, the applicants receive a receipt via e-mail confirming that their proposal was received. The proposals are stored in a secure, password-protected file store in the EU. Each proposal is assigned a unique identifier number which will precede the file name of the proposal itself and of all supporting or relating files to facilitate keeping them together. All proposals are recorded in a data base which will later on also be used to monitor the processes as described below.

3) Eligibility Check

The proposals are checked by the eLTER PLUS Access Team against the criteria set out in this document. In case of minor errors, such as an omitted field in the application template, the applicants are contacted and the errors corrected. In case a proposal fails the eligibility check (experience shows that this is, unfortunately, sometimes the case), the respective user group will receive a formal rejection letter explaining the reason for the rejection.

4) Plausibility Check

For all sites which have received one or more proposals, the respective site owner representatives or PIs (principle investigators) are requested to check the proposal(s) for plausibility:

- Regarding the site: Are the proposed activities doable at the site in terms of natural and structural circumstances (existing equipment, possible additional equipment needs, IT infrastructure, data records available, etc.)?
- Regarding personnel: Will it be possible to provide all the support the users will need to conduct the proposed project?
- Regarding logistics: Can the proposed project logistically be handled, e.g. moving around at the site, accommodation on-site or nearby, etc.
- Regarding physical access (TA only): Does the proposal justify an in-person visit to the site? In case of user groups: Is the size of the group reasonable or could a smaller group do the work just as well?
- Regarding possible restrictions: Is the proposed work in line with all pertinent regulations (e.g. it does not contravene restrictions in terms of health and safety, environmental protection, etc.)
- Furthermore, site owners are asked to rank the projects as a recommendation which ones should be selected.

Experience shows that rarely, but nevertheless now and then, proposals fail the plausibility check. In this case, again, the proposal is formally rejected. Regarding minor deviations, such as an overly large user group, the practice applied is similar to the eligibility check in that certain adaptations may be performed in consultation with the respective user group.

5) Scientific evaluation

The eLTER PLUS selection panel consists of representatives of the institutions which own or operate the sites which are made accessible through the access scheme. For the evaluation of top-down call related proposals, researchers representing the respective research challenges in the eLTER PLUS project may be involved as well.

Proposal evaluations will be anonymous in that the proposers will be informed about the outcome of the evaluation results, but they will not know who has written them.

All applications received by the call deadline and which have passed the eligibility and the plausibility check will be evaluated whereby the following cases are distinguished:

- A site has received one or more proposal(s) which can be funded within the site's TA budget (possibly after a minor reduction of the requested budget). In this case, the proposal(s) will receive one scientific evaluation.
- A site has received proposals requesting funds exceeding the site's TA budget, that is a choice must be made, even in case all proposals are positively evaluated. In this case, the proposals will receive two independent evaluations.
- Multi-site proposals will always receive two independent evaluations.
- If two evaluations of the same proposal significantly deviate, a third evaluation will be conducted.

Evaluators should evaluate proposals which are in line with their personal expertise and which do not cause any conflict of interest. To ascertain transparency, fairness and impartiality, nobody may evaluate proposals requesting access to their own site, nor proposals by users from their own country. Furthermore, the evaluation pool members will be requested to choose from the received projects list considering their own qualifications and to avoid any possible bias.

Evaluation criteria are:

- Scientific quality (innovative, original, well founded?)
- Approach and methodology (adequate, clear, consistent?)
- Relevance for eLTER (in line with programme goals?)

For bottom-up calls: Each matter will be rated on a point scale of 5 (excellent) to 1 (poor) with a weighting of 2 : 2 : 1. That is, a proposal can receive up to 25 points. The thresholds for passing the evaluation (before weighting) are 3, 3, 2. That is, if a proposal e.g., receives 5 points for a convincing scientific idea, but the approach is described in a rather nebulous manner and receives only 2 points, the proposal has failed the evaluation. There is no overall threshold value.

For top-down calls: The third criterion will be replaced by

- Relation to the provided framework (good fit, contribution to the research challenge?)

In this case, weighting will be 1.5 : 1.5 : 2, that is, a proposal can again receive up to 25 points. The thresholds will be 3 for each criterion. Again, there is no overall threshold value.

In case a proposal is evaluated excellently for criterion 1 and 2, but rather weakly for criterion 3, it may be shifted to the bottom up call in consultation with the respective users.

Reviewers will use the *eLTER PLUS TA/RA Proposal Evaluation Form (Annex 4)*.

6) Project selection

Final selection of TA project is done by eLTER PLUS Access Team. The decision is primarily based on the outcome of the scientific evaluation. However, in line with H2020 regulations, several further criteria are being applied with less weight: Preference is given to promising young scientists at the start of their career, to scientists who have not previously used the installation, to those who are working in countries where – to the best of our knowledge – no equivalent research infrastructures exist, and to those who are not employed by one of the eLTER PLUS beneficiaries. Furthermore, the gender dimension is considered.

Not least, although site owner representatives are not permitted to evaluate proposals by user groups requesting access to their site, the recommended ranking by these site owners is taken into account.

7) Notification

After project selection is completed, all site owner beneficiaries are notified regarding the projects selected for their site and the resulting TA and travel budgets. The respective users and site personnel should establish contacts. It is recommended that site owners set up a simple contract with their users considering legal matters associated with the TA journey and stay, e.g. insurance of users, travel documents, environmental regulations. This is, however, not mandatory. An example contract is annexed.

At the same time, all applicants receive a formal acceptance letter or rejection letter including contact information of the site staff who will support their work, and the anonymous reviews for their project.

8) Reporting after TA/RA is completed

Within one month after a user group has completed their TA visit or RA programme, they must submit the filled in *eLTER PLUS TA Reporting template (Annex 2)*. It covers the fieldwork performed and the outcomes of their study and provides all information needed by the project to complete its access related reporting obligations towards the European Commission.

Users are expected to publish the outcomes of their project. Thereby, they must mention that their work has received financial support by the project eLTER PLUS, GA 871128, under H2020. The host organisation who provided support during the project shall also be acknowledged. Moreover, users may offer co-authorship to host organisation researcher(s) based on common practice as currently used in science, relating to intellectual input to the respective publication. However, the mere hosting of users should not suffice for co-authorship.

Annex 1: Proposal template to request support for Transnational Access (TA) and/or Remote Access (RA)

General information about the project	
Project title	
Project acronym	
Site(s) to be accessed	
Keywords (up to five, free text)	
Start date of intended access	
Duration of stay in days	
Number of users requesting access	
Information about the applicant(s)	
User group leader or sole applicant (User group member 1)	
First name	
Last name	
Affiliation	
Street and number	
City	
Country	
E-mail	
Telephone	
Recent references (up to five, alternatively a short CV)	
User group member 2	
First name	
Last name	
Affiliation	
Street and number	
City	
Country	
E-mail	
Recent references (up to five, alternatively a short CV)	

User group member 3	
First name	
Last name	
Affiliation	
Street and number	
City	
Country	
E-mail	
Recent references (up to five, alternatively a short CV)	
User group member 4	
First name	
Last name	
Affiliation	
Street and number	
City	
Country	
E-mail	
Recent references (up to five, alternatively a short CV)	
User groups with more than four members may insert more fields as needed.	
Project description	
Short summary (up to 150 words)	Please describe briefly what the project is about, the major research question, or, if applicable, the hypothesis to be tested.
Scientific objectives (up to 250 words)	Explain the aims of the planned project which makes access to an eLTER PLUS site necessary. The objectives should be realistic and achievable within this TA and/or RA related project.
Work to be performed (up to 300 words)	Describe the sequence of activities intend to be performed at the site(s) in a concise and tangible manner. This text should be precise because it will be used by site staff to prepare your visit (provided your application is accepted).

Data to be obtained (summary)	Summarise in a list the data you intend to gather during your TA or RA project.
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Estimated travel costs of the TA users

Travel costs of user group leader or sole applicant (User group member 1)

Total of travel costs (in €)	
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Justification (itemised)	
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Travel costs of user group member 2

Total of travel costs (in €)	
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Justification (itemised)	
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Travel costs of user group member 3

Total of travel costs (in €)	
------------------------------	--

Justification (itemised)	
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Travel costs of user group member 4

Total of travel costs (in €)	
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Justification (itemised)	
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User groups with more than four members may insert more fields as needed.

Costs for accommodation and other expenses of the TA users

There is no need to estimate accommodation and subsistence costs in this application.

Accommodation will either be provided on-site at no costs to the users or site personnel will assist users in obtaining suitable accommodation in the vicinity of the site. In the latter case, the costs incurred by the users will be reimbursed. Costs for food will be covered as actuals or via a flat subsistence rate in line with the usual business practices of the site owning organisation.

Disclaimer (relates to TA, not to RA)

By submitting this proposal, you consent to the following regulation:

Travel arrangements to eLTER PLUS sites shall be the sole responsibility of the applicant(s). Cf. the note about accommodation above.

eLTER PLUS and the operator(s) of the eLTER site(s) you visit shall not be responsible for any injuries, damages, or losses caused to any user group member in connection with any TA given at an eLTER PLUS TA-site. TA users shall have appropriate travel and health insurance and assume complete and full responsibility for any and all passport, visa, vaccination, currency exchange or other entry requirements of each destination, and all safety or security conditions at the TA-sites during the length of their travel and stay.

All user group members must be clear about the legal responsibilities of their employers. eLTER PLUS has no liability to cover the extra costs of unforeseen circumstances related to travel (e.g. delays or cancellations), customs, shipment and logistics, nor has it legal responsibility for the health and welfare, including emergency and accident situations, of those who are awarded TA.

Dissemination of results and data policy (relate to both TA and RA)

By submitting this proposal, you consent to the below statement:

The user (group) confirms that they intend to disseminate the outcomes of their study conducted under the eLTER PLUS TA/RA Scheme. Users representing SMEs (Small and Medium Enterprises) are exempt from this rule.

Whatever data is collected during the visit must be made available to the site owner organisation and to the wider scientific community within a reasonable time frame and without significant delays (recommended time frame: at most two years). Again, SME users are exempt from this rule. The data policy should presume a timely pathway towards Open Access. At the end of the project, or when publications arise during the project, data should be released using a standard Open Data license and be free of intellectual property rights (IPR).

Successful users are kindly requested to provide a description of their visit, including photographs, and to write a blog and/or social media messages during their visit, de-scribing their experiences. This is highly recommended but not mandatory.

Furthermore, by submitting this proposal, you consent to the option that eLTER PLUS or eLTER site operators may use photographs for dissemination purposes which show you performing work at their sites.

Annex 2: Reporting template for users who have been granted Transnational Access (TA) and/or Remote Access (RA)

Note: the general information at the beginning of this template is identical to the information on the proposal template and can be pasted in, unless changes have occurred.

General information about the project	
Project title	
Project acronym	
Site(s) accessed	
Keywords (up to five, free text)	
Start date of access	
Duration of stay in days	
Number of users granted access	
Information about the user(s)	
User group leader or sole applicant (User group member 1)	
First name	
Last name	
Affiliation	
Street and number	
City	
Country	
E-mail	
Telephone	
Recent publications (up to five, alternatively a short CV)	
User group member 2	
First name	
Last name	
Affiliation	
Street and number	
City	
Country	
E-mail	
Recent publications (up to five, alternatively a short CV)	

User group member 3	
First name	
Last name	
Affiliation	
Street and number	
City	
Country	
E-mail	
Recent publications (up to five, alternatively a short CV)	
User group member 4	
First name	
Last name	
Affiliation	
Street and number	
City	
Country	
E-mail	
Recent publications (up to five, alternatively a short CV)	
User groups with more than four members may insert more fields as needed.	
Report on the work performed	
Activities performed (up to 300 words)	Please describe the steps taken, instrumentation used, techniques employed, data sources consulted etc.
Scientific results (up to 300 words)	Summarise the outcomes of your study at the site(s).
Interpretation of the results (up to 300 words)	Discuss the data obtained and describe the major scientific conclusions drawn.
Main achievements and difficulties during the TA related work (up to 250 words)	Describe what you found especially rewarding during your stay at the site(s), and also any problems that occurred.

Intended publications	Explain where and how you expect to publish the outcomes of your project work.
Feedback	
Please rate the below matters on a scale from 1 (excellent) to 5 (poor). Specific comments will be appreciated.	
Practical information on how to apply for Access and the overall application process	
Information provided, once your project was accepted, on how to proceed	
Support received at the site(s) regarding technical/scientific matters and logistics	
Overall impression of communication and interaction after finishing your TA/RA related work	
Any further comments you may have to improve future TA/RA in the framework of eLTER PLUS	

Annex 3: eLTER PLUS TA/RA Proposal Evaluation Form

Please fill in one form per proposal, write only into the white fields. When you save the file please replace "ID" in the file name with the ID of the proposal. Before filling in the form, please read the document *The eLTER PLUS Transnational Access (TA) and Remote Access (RA) Scheme*, particularly the section on evaluation.

Reviewer name		
Reviews are anonymous. The applicant(s) will receive the part of the table below this line		
Proposal ID		
Proposal name		
Plausibility check by site personnel	passed	
Scientific quality (innovative, original, well founded?)	Please rate from 5 (excellent) to 1 (poor)	
Short justification of your rating		
Approach and methodology (adequate, clear, consistent?)	Please rate from 5 (excellent) to 1 (poor)	
Short justification of your rating		
For bottom up calls: Relevance for LTER goals	Please rate from 5 (excellent) to 1 (poor)	
Short justification of your rating		
For top down calls: Relation to the provided framework	Please rate from 5 (excellent) to 1 (poor)	
Short justification of your rating		

Annex 4: eLTER PLUS TA Administration for Site Owners

This document addresses the representatives of the site owning institutions, not the users. It covers various administrative aspects that should be considered when offering TA in the framework of eLTER PLUS. It is based on practical experiences made in the predecessor project and on questions raised by various site owners. It relates specifically to TA and not to RA. The latter is far easier to administer because no funds are distributed to users and site personnel performs all the practical work.

Agreements with TA users

The acceptance letters sent to the users provide a formal basis for their visit at your site. These letters were sent to you as well and they are all available at the project file store. It is recommended that you set up a simple agreement with your users regarding matters which may cause problems, such as potential risks for the users (especially bodily injuries) and users' insurance obligations, data policy and licences, possible damage to instrumentation caused by users and the like. An example for such an agreement is annexed. There is of course no need to set up anything new for eLTER PLUS if you already have such document(s) from previous instances of offering TA. There is no programme (H2020) or eLTER PLUS project related requirement to set up any contracts with users.

Exact duration of the stay

For each user (group) there is a fixed amount of days at the site. We always count days for the users combined, not the duration of the stay of a group (e.g., a group of 2 users visits the site for 5 days, this makes 10 days for the users combined). This amount is in most cases equal to the amount of days the user (group) has applied for, but in some cases the amount of days was reduced (if so, it is mentioned in the acceptance letter). The granted total amount of days offered per user project is listed in the respective acceptance letter.

If a user (group) finishes earlier, their stay may of course be shorter than planned. Likewise, if a user group needs more time, you may allow them to stay longer at your own costs.

It is recommended that you count weekend days only if some staff will supervise/support the users during the weekends, otherwise not. In the latter case, they could access the site on their own if this is acceptable to you. Of course, if they take off during the weekend, these days do not count as TA days, but you will still pay the accommodation for them and these costs are eligible for reimbursement through your cost statement.

Your TA costs

There is a clear division between the way you charge to the eLTER PLUS project your costs and the users' costs.

Your costs for providing access are covered by the unit or actual costs you calculated per user/day.

If you charge actual costs, you must be able to provide the same records as for any other project related work, such as time-tracking by the personnel involved, bills for consumables and travel etc. The financial administration of offering TA is in this case no different from any other project related work.

However, if you charge unit costs, then your actual costs for offering TA do not need to be identified and you do not need any of the above records for your costs statement.

Nevertheless, for those who charge unit costs, personnel time spent with users will neither be charged as personnel actual costs nor as personnel unit costs (column A in Annex 2 of the Grant Agreement), but they are encompassed in your special unit costs (column F in Annex 2 of the Grant Agreement). Specifically, this means how much TA money you charge to the project exclusively depends on how many days the users spent at your site, and not on how much personnel effort this has caused for you.

The unit cost is part of the Grant Agreement and will stay the same throughout the project, unless you wish to change it in the framework of a Grant Agreement amendment. Please remember that TA unit costs are total costs, that is: direct plus indirect costs.

The project will not cover any costs beyond the budgeted ones, unless otherwise agreed, that is, if you intend to e.g. have users stay longer and wish to be reimbursed for this purpose, ask the eLTER PLUS access administration team before.

The users' costs

User's costs will be covered by the site owning organisation. There is no mechanism for central (i.e. through the project management) costs reimbursement to TA users.

The users' costs encompass travel, room and board, but no personnel costs. For reasons of simplicity, please count the duration of the stay in full days and do not use fractions of TA-days.

The above-mentioned TA unit costs are exclusively for you. Therefore, you have a separate budget as part of your Other costs (which is actual costs and direct for that reason). From this budget, you will reimburse the users costs. Our financial rules for this are:

- Users should book a lowest-cost travel arrangement, such as economy airfare, second-class train, etc.
- You will reimburse the users' actual travel costs (based on invoices) but not the budgeted ones.
- Addition: Users must provide to you all bills, e.g. flight e-tickets, B&B-bills, car rental bills, etc. You must keep the original bills in the same way as you keep the bills for your own travels and other direct costs. A simple travel costs claim form for the users will make the process easier for you. It is recommended that you apply your usual practices for travel costs reimbursement.
- Travel costs can also include freight charges for instruments, if they are necessary for the planned work. Before booking any freights, the TA users should however check

with site personnel if such instrument already exists at the site, or if it can e.g. be borrowed from a local research team, making the costs more affordable.

- If on-site accommodation is available, users should use it. The costs will be covered by your user travel budget, the same is true for on-site meals.
- Otherwise, users should use reasonable off-site accommodation and restaurants. Site managers are kindly requested to assist them in finding such places.
- Rental car costs including fuel can be reimbursed if justified, that is, if the site or places within the site cannot be accessed otherwise, or if rental car usage is cheaper than public transport (which is the case for some user groups); rental cars should be reasonable, e.g., in most cases there is no need for expensive 4-wheelers.
- There is no rule for calculating daily allowances, but please use your usual business practices, e.g. pay to them the same amount an employee of your organisation would receive for business travel within your country. Obviously, the amount will take into consideration whether on-site accommodation and/or meals are available or not.
- Note: If you cover all costs including meals, there is obviously no need to pay any daily allowances.

Records

Users are obliged to fill in the eLTER PLUS TA Reporting Template (Annex 2, available to them from the project website) before you reimburse their costs. You are kindly requested to collect this form from the users (one per group of course) and hand it to the eLTER PLUS Access Team. The template is intentionally very similar to the proposal form, and thus, a part can be copied and pasted. Please insist on this template being filled in, and check whether it was done correctly and completely, especially regarding the persons who were really there (may not always be the same as the ones in the proposal) and also check the total number of days, because there have been misunderstandings in this regard.

Questions

In case you have further questions, do not hesitate to ask the eLTER PLUS TA coordinator: herbert.haubold@umweltbundesamt.at

Annex 5: Example eLTER PLUS TA agreement

Note: It is recommended that site operating organisations conclude this or another simple agreement with their users. For user groups, one agreement should be set up to be signed by all of the group's members or, alternatively, individual agreements can be provided.

The TA visitor and PI (principle investigator or site manager) of the infrastructure have discussed the planned project and have agreed on: (please tick the appropriate boxes)

- working regulations at the site, including insurance for the people involved
- technical access to be provided
- measurement infrastructure services to be provided
- installation of visiting instruments during the project
- sharing, reporting and publishing of the data and research results

The TA application has been evaluated by the eLTER PLUS project and both the visitor seeking access and the principal investigator granting access have confirmed the project.

TA Site: _____ Country: _____

Name of visitor	gender	nationality	start date	end date	no days

Upon signing this agreement, the TA visitor(s) agree(s) to follow the TA and site instructions, including data policy and licenses at the site. The TA visitor(s) agree(s) to have his/her/their own insurance, covering all work-related liabilities, bodily injuries and possible damage to instrumentation caused by them. The costs for the TA visitor(s) will be reimbursed according to the eLTER PLUS TA rules. The TA visitor(s) are obliged to fill in the eLTER PLUS TA Project Summary Report after their project work is concluded.

Date, Place: _____

Full Name (TA Site Manager): _____

Signature:

Date, Place: _____

Full Name (TA User): _____

Signature:

Date, Place: _____

Full Name (TA User): _____

Signature:

Date, Place: _____

Full Name (TA User): _____

Signature:

Date, Place: _____

Full Name (TA User): _____

Signature:

Date, Place: _____

Full Name (TA User): _____

Signature: